

Materials Informatics Approach to Predictive Models for Elastic Modulus of Polypropylene Composites

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Introduction

Example application of composites

- Battery module covers
- Interior materials of aircraft
- Interior materials of automobile
- ...

Three elemental materials of composites

Vast number of combinations among these materials

↓
Almost unable to consider all of them by human

↓
Machine learning method can be useful to obtain valuable candidates for measurement

However, the detail information (physical property etc...) of these components are often NOT-acquirable in an actual corporate research.

Purpose

To establish a machine learning method to predict target properties by using only categorical information

Information about brand names

Base polymer : m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots

Additive : a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots

Filler : f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots

Machine Learning

Target Property

Ex. Elastic modulus, etc...

Method

1. Featurizing formulation of composites

Experimental setting in this research

Target Property	Control Parameter		
Elastic Modulus	PP	Additive	Filler
	11	17	20

Recipe of a composite			
Component	PP	Additive	Filler
Name	$m_i (i = 1-11)$	$a_j (j = 1-17)$	$f_k (k = 1-20)$
Mass ratio	1	x_{aj}	x_{fk}

Representing a recipe by using dummy variables

$$\mathbf{x} = (0, \dots, \underset{i}{1}, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, \underset{j}{x_{aj}}, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, \underset{k}{x_{fk}}, \dots, 0)$$

We use this \mathbf{x} as a feature to predict an elastic modulus. The dimension of \mathbf{x} : $11 + 17 + 20 = 48$.

2. Partial Least Square (PLS) Method

Dummy variable representing a recipe \mathbf{x} → PLS → Predicted elastic modulus \mathbf{y}

3. Evaluation & Analysis

1. Evaluating constructed PLS model by predicting test data
2. Performing actual experiment to check prediction results
3. Analyzing the experimental results comparing the model prediction

Result & Discussion

The result of PLS regression for elastic modulus

※ The hyperparameter of PLS was optimized by LOOCV

The model with a significant accuracy was constructed. However, a few data points were outlier (red circle).

PLS : Linear regression model

The observed elastic modulus behaves non-linearly against x_{16} value.

The constructed model can not predict this data point because of non-linearity for content ratio.

Material	PP	Filler	Additive
Component	x_4	x_{16}	x_{31}
Ratio	55	40	5

Evaluating test data by performing actual measurement

575484 candidates were predicted by the constructed model.

q_1, q_2 : PLS components

Summaring these results...

Around a lot of training data... ⇒ **Possibly well-predicted!**

Sparse training data points or almost nothing... ⇒ **Low prediction accuracy...**

Conclusion & Future Work

1. Elastic property of composites can be predicted by using only categorical information of materials. ⇒ We can obtain valuable recipes from vast number of candidates.
2. The prediction accuracy can be checked by visualizing a feature space of a regression model. ⇒ To evaluate the reliability of the prediction, a Bayesian approach will be applied.

To consider the interaction between materials for more precise prediction...

⇒ See poster #1130 & "M. Okuyama et al., Sci. Technol. Adv. Methods., 2, 1, 106-118 (2022)."

The prediction errors of E & H were relatively large. H ⇒ Far away from training data as well as the above case. E ⇒ Sparse training data points